

Capacity Building As A Correlate Of Teachers' Competence To Teach Economics: A Case Study Of Ilembedistrict, South Africa

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 22, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : People Empowerment, Skills Development, Training And Development, Teacher Development</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5234073</p>	<p><i>Capacity building programmes play a vital role in teachers' competence and development. While several studies have been conducted on the impact of capacity building of industrial workers on productivity, few research exists on the university capacity building programme for school teachers. Thus, this paper explores capacity building initiative of the University of Zululand in the teaching of Economics at Ilembe district in South African schools. In this regard, quantitative investigation methodology was followed. A case study approach was adopted to gather data from respondents. Questionnaires were administered to elicit information from respondents. Data gathered from questionnaires were triangulated with information provided by document analysis so that conclusions could be made. The findings of this investigation revealed that there should be ongoing capacity building workshop for teachers of Economics in Grades 10, 11 and 12. The investigation further revealed that teachers' qualifications in the subject must be improved by the KZNDBE Ilembe District.</i></p>

Introduction

Forging strategic partnerships with other stakeholders could lead to positive teaching and learning outcomes for learners, teachers and parents in schools. This demonstrates that working together might lead to positive solutions if all parties commit themselves for common purpose. School management team members such as heads of departments, deputy principals and principals must create conducive environments for teachers to seek assistance on content knowledge where it is deemed necessary. This paper reports on the investigation in which teachers of Economics were offered capacity building workshop in the teaching of Economics at Ilembe District.

Background of the 'Going-Up' project in Economics

The KwaZulu-Natal Department of Basic Education (KZNDBE) Ilembe District is located, managed and led in KwaDukuza town, formerly Stanger in the democratic Republic of South Africa. It covers the following areas, namely Gingindlovu, Kranskop, KwaDukuza, Mandeni, Maphumulo and Ndwedwe. The District has been identified as one of those that tend to underperform in the teaching of Economics in Grade 12. The District director approached the University of Zululand to assist with subject specialists for subjects that are regarded as 'killer subjects'. The matter was communicated to the Dean of the Faculty of Education in order to solicit support for the 'Going-Up' project in Economics. The matter was discussed at faculty level, and members were willing to collaborate with KZNDBE Ilembe District. One of the authors of this paper, namely Dr A.B. Buthelezi was seen suitable to lead this capacity building initiative for Economics' teachers. The onus was then on Dr A.B. Buthelezi to set up a team which was going to be involved in terms of planning, implementation and evaluation of the project. The team comprises lecturers in the Faculties of Education and Commerce as well as Administration and Law. In the nutshell that is how the capacity building workshop for Economics started. However, the project leader is going to recruit Maths, Accounting and Physical Science lecturers to be part of the project in the near future. Grade 12 Economics' teachers attend blocked sessions once a term of the school calendar.

Capacity building workshop for Grade 12 Economics' teachers started on the 3rd up to the 5th of August 2019 at Amatikulu Public Health Training (PHT) Centre in the Nyoni area. KZNDBE Ilembe District had a total number of 2 826 learners, 98 teachers and 98 schools in 2019.

The involvement of the University of Zululand came at the propitious time when KZNDBE Ilembe District was in dire need of capacity building workshop for teachers who are teaching Economics in Grade 12. The table below provides synopsis of the Grade 12 class for Economics in 2018.

When capacity building workshop was conducted there were 67 teachers in the KZNDBE Ilembe District who were less than 35 years of age teaching Economics in Grade 12. This shows that Economics is being taught by young teachers who might need to be mentored or capacitated in the subject. A total number of 30 teachers were between 35 and 55 years of age. One could expect mature, knowledgeable and skilled teachers to be in this category. The majority of teachers who are teaching Economics in KZNDBE Ilembe District are not involved in senior management positions. KZNDBE Ilembe District comprises teachers who are Africans and Indians. The majority of teachers of Economics were African females. It is probable that the subject tends to appeal more to female teachers compared to their male counterparts. There was no teacher who had physical disability. The KZNDBE District is largely female-dominated in nature.

Teaching qualifications for Economics' teachers seemed to be a major concern for KZNDBE Ilembe District officials during capacity building workshop. When teachers were asked to write their qualifications, it was discovered that most teachers had levels one and two of their studies in Economics as a subject. Some teachers never had any educational qualifications in Economics. Others were teaching specialists in Accounting, Business Management, and Human Resource Management. There were very few teachers who had studied Economics up to third year level at the university. Poor or lack of teaching qualifications might have an adverse impact on learner outcomes in the subject. Challenges pertaining to teacher qualifications call for KZNDBE to make funds available for human resource development initiative.

The University of Zululand became involved in the capacity building of teachers in the KZNDBE Ilembe District of KwaZulu-Natal province in 2019. Great strides have been made to date on the basis of ensuring that there is partnership of higher education institutions with the Department of Basic Education in South Africa.

Teachers have shown great enthusiasm and ability to teach Economics at Grade 12 since the arrival of the University of Zululand. It is critical that the Department of Higher Education and Training, and together with the Department of Basic Education should work together in the pursuit of common goals. Higher education institutions should be able to fill in content knowledge gaps which might have occurred during years of academic training. There is also no doubt that self-esteem and self-actualisation needs of employees could be enhanced through capacity building initiative.

KZNDBE Ilembe District is actively involved throughout the process of arranging capacity building workshop. The subject adviser and other colleagues in the Teaching and Learning Services - Further Education and Training (TLS-FET) participate in the processes of arranging workshop venue, communicating information, and other logistical arrangements such as food and hostels for teachers. This initiative tends to enjoy buy-in on the part of senior management and leadership in the KZNDBE Ilembe District. For instance, the director of KZNDBE Ilembe District encourages supportive teaching and learning initiative which could enhance performance of teachers and learners in schools. This is what researchers tend to regard as servant leadership undertakings on the part of the management and leadership component of KZNDBE Ilembe District.

Capacity building workshop is budgeted by the KZNDBE Ilembe District and the University of Zululand, Faculty of Education. KZNDBE Ilembe District further receives sponsorships from Old Mutual, Ilembe District Municipality, Isibaya Casino, and local business leaders to run capacity building workshop for teachers of Economics. On the other hand, the University of Zululand, Faculty of Education tends to receive money from investigation institutions like National Investigation Fund (NRF) and others to run the project.

Resources for capacity building workshop are provided by the University of Zululand and KZNDBE Ilembe District. The following resources were given to respondents: Winter Support Document 2019; Teacher Guide for Winter Support Document 2019; Last Mile Revised 2019; 2016 -2018 Previous Question Papers, and Workbook material for Grade 12.

The University of Zululand, Faculty of Education provides food and vehicle which might be needed by facilitators. Furthermore, the University of Zululand makes necessary arrangements with the sister Faculty of Commerce, Administration and Law (FCAL) so that lecturers who are specialists in Economics could be released to facilitate capacity building workshop for teachers in the KZNDBE Ilembe District. Resources for workshop or plenary sessions such as marking pens, charts, overhead projector and laptop are provided by the KZNDBE Ilembe District.

Facilitators bring to the fore their teaching expertise and experience in the field of Economics. The subject adviser collects information regarding problematic topics or units in Economics from teachers prior to capacity building workshop. Teachers in the KZNDBE Ilembe District identified the following problematic topics prior to capacity building workshop: perfect market, oligopoly, monopolistic competition, monopoly, economic indicators, inflation, business cycles, and foreign exchange markets. The researchers observed during the

capacity building session that some teachers have a selective practice of teaching certain units or topics. This could be ascribed to the challenging nature of some units or topics.

Capacity building workshop also serves as networking platforms for teachers of Economics. During the plenary sessions teachers are able to exchange contact details so that they can share information or reading materials. Teachers who might be struggling on certain topics are able to identify someone who can be a mentor. This paper has greatly emphasised the need for networking amongst teachers.

Timing for capacity building workshop must be evaluated so that necessary changes could be implemented. This task is conducted by University of Zululand's facilitators and KZNDBE Ilembe District officials. The onus is on KZNDBE Ilembe District officials to attend to logistical arrangements pertaining to outsourcing the caterer; choice and accessibility of the workshop venue; attendance registers; availability of ablutions; first aid equipment, food menu options; duration of the workshop session; plenary sessions; accommodation; health and safety measures, and duplication of reading materials.

Facilitators from the University of Zululand covered the following topics during the capacity building workshop: Social and Economic Indicators; Inflation; Environmental Sustainability; Circular Flow; Business Cycles, and Public Sector.

Capacity building initiative must be evaluated on the basis of its usefulness in the process of learning acquisition. This process tends to assist facilitators and education authorities to make sense of capacity building workshop and to a larger extent address some of the challenges pertaining to implementation. Effectiveness of presentations during capacity building sessions is conducted by teachers themselves, since they are the ones who should acquire knowledge and skills. On the other hand, evaluations assist facilitators to revisit their facilitation strategies. Evaluation of capacity building sessions also serves as a strategic approach on the part of KZNDBE officials in terms of assessing attainment of learning outcomes so that improvements can be made.

Literature Review

The importance of capacity building

Teachers need to keep abreast on their pedagogical content knowledge, the psychology of the learners and new research on teaching and learning. [Markus, Hietajärvi, atischek-Jauk, and Kirsti \(2019\)](#) notes that teachers are expected to step up the effort and develop their knowledge and skills to be able to develop learners' social competences. Hence, they need appropriate capacitation (Tuncel&Çobanoğlu, 2018). Capacity building has been well recognised globally because today's teachers' roles and accountabilities have changed drastically. For instance, even the qualifications of the teaching-learning process itself have changed (Mahlangu, 2016). Omar (2014) supports the above assertion when he stresses that capacity building is important because of the new challenges that teachers face as well as the changes in education globally. He further argues that capacity building enables teachers to understand and implement the modified school curriculum according to its requirements, aims and objectives, to improve and enhance the necessary skills as well as to interpret the concept changes accurately. Furthermore, Tuncel and Çobanoğlu (2018) depict that the World Bank Report (2018) reported that a survey of 38 developed and developing countries found that 91 per cent of teachers had participated in professional development in the previous 12 months and Two-thirds of World Bank projects with an education component in the last decade incorporated teacher professional development.

Capacity building is essential because it promotes quality teaching (Martin & Thomson, 2018). Harjantoa, Liea, Wihardinib, Pryor and Wison (2018) stress that teaching quality is pivotal because it has a vital effect on teachers' performance and professionalism (Nzarirwehi&Atuhumuze, 2019). In supporting the above assertion, Omar (2014) further states that it updates teachers' skills and knowledge for improving their teaching and learning because learners are expected to be taught by teachers who are committed, competent and effective. Hence, Harjantoa, et al. (2018) state that learners' achievement is determined more by teacher effectiveness which includes their preparedness on their pedagogical content knowledge (PCK). Thus, the capacity building shows a significant effect on teachers' academic qualifications, their performance as well as their professionalism (Nzarirwehi&Atuhumuze, 2019).

A majority of results on capacity building reveal that there was a positive impact on teachers after they had been capacitated. For instance, Harjantoa, et al. (2018) report the findings of various studies on teacher professional development programmes that reveal the significant effects of teacher development on improving learners' achievement. On the same vein, the results of the workshop conducted by [Markus, Hietajärvi, atischek-Jauk, Kirsti \(2019\)](#) when they were investigating the possible change in teachers' knowledge, their applied knowledge, and their sense of competence during the Lions Quest (LQ) workshop. They revealed that the intervention had a positive effect on the participants across all samples apart from one. Moreover, teachers benefitted even on social and emotional learning (SEL). Hence, successful SEL enables both teachers and learners to face their

daily challenges more easily, no matter where and how they come. Omar (2014) concurs with the above-mentioned assertions when he stresses that capacity building puts teachers at the centre of any improvement effort. Similarly, Schleicher (2015) accentuates that teachers who attend the teacher development programme, feel more confident and better prepared than those teachers who do not attend such programmes.

Martin and Thomson (2018:10) argue that "teacher learning must shift from an emphasis on the individual towards the concept of teacher-learning communities recognising the importance of engagement arising from the particular contexts and institutions in which teachers practice".

The above suggestion demonstrates that even if teachers can meet the required standard of qualification but they have to be the life-long learners to be abreast and be able to create authentic situations for learners to learn. This implies that no matter how good pre-service training for teachers is, but it cannot prepare teachers for all the challenges they will face throughout their careers (OECD, 2009). Similarly, Harjantoa, et al. (2018) opine that teachers' qualifications only do not increase teachers' quality nor learners' attainment.

Universities and school partners should work collaboratively to improve learning for all teachers, including pre-service teachers (Livy, Vale & Herbert, 2014 and Mahlangu, 2018). Furthermore, Tuncel and Çobanoğlu (2018) stress that seasoned teachers, as well as novice teachers' capacitation, have to be aligned with the needs and requirements of the institutions they work in. Omar (2014) concurs with Tuncel and Çobanoğlu (2018) when he argues that teachers are expected to implement educational reforms under the aspiration of the National Philosophy of Education.

The above assertions depict the reason why Martin and Thomson (2018) argue that teachers' capacity building is one of the models of the on-going or continuous professional development (CPD) or in-service of teachers because it enhances their teaching. However, according to Cooper, Sparks and Richardson (Nzarirwehi&Atuhumuze, 2019) professional development is a recurring process instigated by changes in knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes among teachers and other education service sector workers towards improving learning outcomes. On the other hand, in-service teacher training is a central component of professional development of teachers that has been adopted by policymakers and education departments to orient teachers and equip them with skills aimed at enhancing the quality of education. Never the less, there is strong evidence that for a school to achieve effectiveness and improvement in academic achievement, it has to engage its teachers in capacity building.

Research question

What are the results of capacity building initiative in the teaching of Economics in South African schools?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is underpinned by positivism paradigm since the researchers sought to evaluate the phenomenon objectively, and to describe its nature and effects. It adopted quantitative methodology in data collection to explore capacity building initiative at the University of Zululand in the teaching of Economics in South African. The case study approach was thereafter used in this evaluation.

Population and sampling

The Ilembe district in KwaZulu-Natal province in South Africa has 98 high schools which offer Economics in grade 12. This study targeted schools which underperformed in Grade 12 in Economics. There are 39 schools which underperformed in Economics in grade 12. Subsequently, 39 teachers were invited to attend capacity building workshop. Only one teacher who was representing one of the school which underperformed never attended the workshop. The sample of the study ended up being 38. They ultimately formed a purposive selected sample of this study.

Research instruments

Two research instruments were used for data collection, namely document analyses and questionnaire. The researchers wanted to triangulate data provided by the respondents. This view is supported by McMillan and Schumacher (2010:331) when they affirm that "different strategies may yield different insights about a topic of interest and thus result to the credibility of findings." Additionally, DeVos, Strydom, Fouche and Delport (2011:442) stress that triangulation's main advantage is that "each type of datum can be collected and analysed separately and independently." Hence, two methods were employed to collect data from the sample.

Document analyses

Document analyses in the KZNDBE Ilembe District showed that 7% of the candidates in 2018 performed below 30% pass rate. There were 11% of the candidates who were between 30% and 49,9%. A total of 13% of the candidates were between 50% and 59,9%. There were 12% of the candidates who achieved between 60% and 69,9%. A total of 10% of the candidates received between 70% and 79,9%. A sizeable number of 33% of

candidates achieved between 80% and 100%. The overall pass percentage of the KZNDE Ilembe District in 2018 was 64,69% in Economics. This performance in 2018 necessitated intervention from other stakeholders in order to improve pass rate in the KZNDBE Ilembe District.

A comparative analysis of Grade 12 Economics results at KZNDBE Ilembe District between 2017 and 2019 was conducted. In 2017 KZNDBE Ilembe District received 61,69% pass rate. However, there was slight improvement in 2018 since it recorded 64, 12% pass rate. As a result of the University of Zululand's capacity building initiative there has been significant impact on Grade 12 Economics' pass rate in the KZNDBE Ilembe District since there it achieved 65%. It is evident that teachers' content knowledge of the subject has improved. On the other side, learners' performance has also dramatically increased. In this regard, one may confidently state that the future looks good for these capacity building initiative of the University of Zululand in the teaching of Economics at Grade 12. The interventions have not yet achieved the target set by the KZNDBE Ilembe District which is 80% pass rate. Furthermore, the KZNDBE Ilembe District has put it as its target that there should be no school obtaining less than 30% in Economics as from 2019 and beyond.

The KZNDBE Ilembe District has provided some guidelines on quality assurance measures. According to the District officials, quality is based on the level of achievement attained by learners in Grade 12. For instance, the subject adviser says an overall performance in Economics should be between 80% and 100% (levels 6 and 7). There were 33 schools which performed between 80% and 100% (levels 6 and 7).

Questionnaires

Questionnaires with closed-ended questions were used in this investigation. The closed-ended questions were asking the respondents to make choices from a set of alternatives. The Likert Scale was used to provide alternative answers - *strongly disagree (SD)*, *disagree (D)*, neutral (N), *agree (A)*, *strongly agree (SA)*. The questionnaires were appropriate to meet investigation objective in the sense that they provided respondents adequate time to reflect on the proceedings of the capacity building workshop. The questionnaires were also chosen since they allow respondents to remain anonymous.

There were 38 teachers who attended the capacity building workshop at Amatikulu PHT centre. One teacher did not attend the capacity building workshop. This demonstrates that most teachers are serious in terms of improving their content knowledge in Economics. It should, however, be borne in mind that the workshop catered for teachers in schools who achieved less than 50% pass rate in the National Senior Certificate in 20.

Two research instruments were used for data collection. They are document analysis and questionnaire. During capacity building workshop teachers wrote pre-test and post-test activities. Pre-test activities are used to determine teachers' knowledge in the subject whilst post-test activities are used to ascertain knowledge and skills acquired during capacity building workshop. Questionnaires for both pre-test and post-test activities are administered by the subject adviser. After data analysis for pre-test and post-test activities the subject adviser remarked:

There was slightly improvement when we compared Pre-Test and Post-Test scores. The averages for Pre-Test was 56% and Post-Test was 71%.

Capacity building sessions start at 8h00 till 17h00. The mode of facilitation tends to be very interactive in nature since it takes into cognisance the fact that teachers come to workshop with basic knowledge of the Economics. The process of facilitating capacity building workshop moreover considers conditions for adult learning. Learning activities are offered in groups so that teachers can work on certain scenarios. This strategy encourages collaborative learning practices. Teachers are also allowed to indicate areas which are problematic in Economics as a subject. However, some information about problematic areas in the subject may be gleaned from respondents during pre-test and post-test activities.

Table 1: Biographical information of respondents (n=38)

For investigation of this magnitude, it was deemed necessary to determine dynamics pertaining to biographical information of respondents so that inferences can be made. Biographical information of Economics' teachers in the KZNDBE Ilembe District provides peculiar information pertaining to their ages. Most respondents were less than 35 years of age. The high rate of youngsters in the teaching of Economics could be attributed to the fact that most teachers tend to complete their studies at the younger age. It is also probable that most of them have done three year qualifications at universities.

Data Analysis

Collected data from the closed-ended questionnaires in the quantitative investigation were translated into numerical codes, captured into SPSS version 26 software of a computer programme. Frequencies were calculated by counting how often something appeared in the data and comparing one measurement with others (Hancock, 2002). Data analysis also employed various other statistical tools and tests used for analysis including percentages, reliability analysis, reliability testing, descriptive statistics mean and average scores. Cronbach's alpha was run to assess the reliability, or internal consistency, of pre-posttest scores and Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test was also performed to compare repeated measurements on a single sample to assess whether their population mean ranks differ. This process served to fulfil reliability and validity requirements of the

investigation. Data were presented, interpreted and analysed by the researchers in order to fulfil the objective of this investigation, and to answer the investigation question. Verification of data gathered was conducted by educational management and leadership experts. This process served to fulfil reliability and validity requirements of the investigation.

Results, interpretations and analysis

Cronbach's Alpha was run to test the significance of the difference between pre-workshop and post-workshop. The Alpha value $\alpha = 0.765$ (refer to table 2) meaning that the reliability of the items in the questionnaire were acceptable in the pre-workshop and $\alpha = 0.874$ (refer to table 3) in the post-workshop indicating that the questionnaire was reliable.

Table 4 presents the value that how Cronbach's alpha would be should one of the items was deleted from the scale. The results indicate that the reliability could not be improved substantially should one of the items be removed or deleted from the scale. Statistical inference was also conducted to test for the statistical significance of the difference between the pre-test and post-test replies (refer to table 5). The significance (P-value) is less than 0.001, which means that the means scores per item was significantly higher at the post-test than at the pre-test. The Wilcoxon Signed rank test was also performed on the summary statistics and the results was that the P-value is less than 0.001, meaning that the post-test scores were significantly higher after the workshop than before the workshop.

The table further shows that a significant number of respondents were between 35 and 55 years of age. These are mature teachers who are available in schools. However, the researchers tend to doubt their content knowledge and relevance of their qualifications in terms of teaching Economics as a subject in schools. There were no respondents who were above 55 years of age that were involved in the teaching of Economics.

The shortage of lucrative careers in South Africa might have enticed certain individuals into the teaching profession. Appleton, Morgan & Sives (2006) in SACE (2011) argue that South Africa is in a situation where the rate of teacher attrition currently exceeds the rate at which newly trained teachers are being produced. In this regard, the researchers opine that the shortage of lucrative offers might pose a serious setback in the effective teaching of Economics. During capacity building workshop it was established that some teachers had irrelevant and incomplete qualifications for teaching Economics. Qualified individuals in the subject are easily lured or attracted by organisations in the private sector.

According to the table, the majority of respondents who are teaching Economics are not occupying senior management and leadership positions. This means that there were very few Economics' teachers who were involved in school management and leadership positions.

During capacity building workshop, an overwhelming number of teachers were Africans. It is probable that most of the teachers who attended workshop were coming from schools in the rural areas. There is a great challenge for teachers who teach in rural areas in South Africa in terms of scarcity of teaching and learning resources. KZNDBE Ilembe District comprises schools in urban, peri-urban and rural areas.

An overwhelming number of respondents who attended capacity building workshop were females. It is probable that the teaching of Economics is appealing to female teachers. However, it should be taken into cognisance that South African population is largely female-dominated. There were no Economics' teachers during capacity building workshop who suffered any level of disability.

Table 2: Capacity building workshop evaluation: content, design, instructor, results, and self-pace delivery

The content is relevant to Grades 10-12

An overwhelming number of respondents (89.5%) agreed that the workshop content was relevant to them. This is attributed to the high level of preparedness and content knowledge on the part of facilitators. According to Nzarirwehi and Atuhumuze (2019, 21) new experiences demand new and specifically tailored approaches with regard to teaching methods, which then justifies the need for teachers to be exposed to capacity building programmes from time to time. About (10.5%) of the respondents remained neutral on the issue. The significance (P-value) is less than 0,001, which means that the means scores was significantly higher at the Post-test than at the Pre-test

This workshop lived up to my expectations

There was high number of respondents (81.6%) who affirmed that the workshop lived up to their level of expectation. This means that teachers benefited from capacity building proceedings. There was no waste of time in terms of attending the workshop. Vukelich and Wrenn (1999) Ayvaz-Tuncel and Cobanoglu (2018) emphasize that capacity building initiatives must focus on participants needs and connected to professional practice. On the other hand, Yadav and Bhardwaj (2013) in Nzarirwehi and Atuhumuze (2019, 22) argue that confidence instilled by capacity building training programme facilitates planning and preparation towards effective teaching. However, (18.4%) of the respondents chose to be neutral on the matter.

The workshop activities stimulated my learning

There was significant number of respondents (79%) who felt that the workshop activities stimulated their learning. This demonstrates that most teachers became enthused in terms of learning about Economics subject. There is no doubt that these teachers wanted to change their attitudes so that they could become lifelong learners. This view is endorsed by Nzairwehi and Atuhumuze (2019, 23) that capacity building initiatives must engender change in human behaviour, attitudes, knowledge, skills, and capabilities focussed on cultivating professional etiquette required by teachers to perform adequately at given tasks. Omar (2014) further endorses that the effectiveness of capacity building workshops in schools is related to the attitude of teachers in schools. When reliability was tested an Alpha value of 0.735 was attained meaning that the reliability was acceptable. However, some respondents (2.6%) felt that capacity building workshop never lived up to their expectation and 18.4% were undecided. It is probable that these were teachers who really possessed limited content knowledge in Economics.

The pace of this workshop was appropriate

“Agree” appeared to be the most frequent response after workshop for example 73.7% respondents conceded that the workshop was well-paced compared to 21.1% in the pre-test. Pacing appropriately the workshop allows teachers to grasp the content with ease. On the other hand, Herman (1986) opines that pacing allows attendees to move through a capacity building workshop at different rates and is frequently advocated for increasing or decreasing the content. In this regard, it becomes important on the part of facilitators to understand conditions of adult learning. There were (26.3%) of the respondents who remained neutral on the issue.

The instructor was well prepared

An overwhelming number of respondents, 86.8% indicated that the workshop instructor was well prepared compared to 21%, of respondents in the pre-test. Instructors from the University of Zululand did wonderful job in this regard. This means that they were always prepared for the task at hand. According to Omar (2014, 4) the facilitator’s leadership behaviour is related to the success of the capacity building workshop. There were 10.5% of the respondents who were neutral on this matter.

The instructor was helpful

There was a significant improvement of positive responses from 34.2% pre-test to 84.2% post-test. This means that a significant number of teachers after the workshop felt that the instructor was helpful during presentation. Facilitators adopted an interactive approach in learning. Effective capacity building workshops must cater for long-lasting learning experience and reflectivity (Ayvaz-Tuncel and Cobanoglu, 2018, 159). Workshop attendees were able to ask questions so that they could get clear understanding of the various units or chapters in Economics. A total of 13,2% respondents chose to remain neutral whereas 2,6% respondent disagreed on this matter.

I accomplish the objective of this workshop

There was a significant increase of respondents from 34.2% pre-test to 78.9% who endorsed that the workshop assisted them to accomplish the objectives of the workshop. Effective planning tends to be critical for facilitators in this regard. Workshop attendees need to find value for coming to the workshop. This view is also shared by Tammemagi (2009) that the overall objective of the capacity building workshop should be that the team is further down the road towards achieving the status of a high performing team. This keeps the team thinking forward to where it wants to be. There was a decrease of the respondents from 42.1% pre-test to 21.1% post-test who were neutral on this matter. One (2,63%) questionnaire was spoilt by respondent.

I will be able to use what I learned in this workshop

Most respondents (89.4%) felt that they would use what they learned in the workshop. This demonstrates that Economics’ teachers became confident in terms of what is expected of them when they teach the subject. Ayvaz-Tuncel and Cobanoglu (2018: 160) argue that capacity building workshops should encourage participants to reflect on their teaching. Thus the capacity building workshop afforded teachers with opportunity for transformational learning. However, there were about 10.6% of respondents who were undecided or neutral.

The workshop was a good way for me to learn this content

An overwhelming number of respondents, 84.2% felt that the workshop was a good way for them to learn Economics’ content. Honing skills and content knowledge on the part of teachers should become an ongoing process for the Department of Basic Education and other stakeholders in South Africa. This view is also endorsed by Nzairwehi and Atuhumuze (2019, 21) when they state that continuous development and improvement of professional competence of teachers might yield positive outcomes for learners. This also calls for funds to be made available by the employer. A total of 15.8% respondents remained neutral on this issue.

How would you improve this workshop? (Please tick all applicable sections)

Description	Frequencies	Ranks
Increase the content covered in the workshop	24	1

Update the content covered in the workshop	19	2
Improve the instructional methods	19	2
Make workshop activities more stimulating	17	4
Improve workshop organization	13	5
A lot more time for the workshop	10	6
Make the workshop less difficult	9	7
Speed up the pace of the workshop	7	8
Slow down the pace of the workshop	6	9
Reduce the content covered in the workshop	5	10
Make the workshop more difficult	2	11

The above table shows that most respondents wanted workshop content to be increased. Ayvaz-Tuncel and Cobanoglu (2018, 160) endorsed that teachers need to update their knowledge and skills on curricula, psychology and pedagogy of the learners and new research on teaching and learning; they need appropriate capacity-building workshops. In ranks 2 and 3, respondents felt that the content of the workshop must be increased and that instructional methods should be improved. Making number 4 on the list was that workshop activities must be stimulating. Improving the workshop organisation made number 5. Other respondents indicated that a lot of time for the workshop must be given; the workshop should be made less difficult; the pace of the workshop must be sped up; content covered in the workshop must be reduced, and others felt that workshop should be more difficult.

Which additional improvements would you recommend for this workshop?

Most of the respondents never answered this section. However, some of them suggested the following:

- The facilitators' presentations have to be line with ATP. This requires facilitators to be well-versed with Grade 12 content for Economics. It is pointless to give teachers weapons that they cannot use in class.
- Workshop has to be conducted during weekends not during weekdays. This view does not address real challenges that teachers tend to face in schools. Planning of workshop tends to enjoy the buy-in on the part of senior management in the KZNDBE IlembeDistrict. It should be borne in mind that KZNDBE IlembeDistrict is serious in terms of improving learning outcomes in Grade 12. For instance, it has been highlighted in this paper that the KZNDBE IlembeDistrict is targeting 80 percent pass rate in Economics as from 2019 and beyond. This calls then for appropriate measures to be put in place by the KSNDBE officials so that there could be goal attainment at the end of the day.

General suggestions

Respondents were also afforded opportunity to provide suggestions pertaining to the capacity building workshop. The following suggestions were made:

- Workshop should be aligned with Grade 12 Annual Teaching Plan (ATP) and examination guidelines.
- Teachers need Teach- A- Learner programme to be implemented.
- Workshops for Grades 10 and 11 must be provided.

The suggestions provided by respondents demonstrate that there is great need for planning of the capacity building workshops. The respondents also demonstrated that workshops for learners in Economics need to be catered for. The respondents were also futuristic in their suggestions when they indicated workshops for Grades and 11. This requires that KZNDBE must budget for such workshops.

Conclusion

The capacity building workshop of economics teachers in Ilembe district had a significant effect on improving the perception of participants and therefore, improving the economics results. It is evident that capacity building workshops produce fruitful results if both the facilitators and the people who are capacitated are committed to what they are doing. For example, the improvement of the Economics results for Grade 12 in Ilembe district confirms this view. Additionally, it is imperative that universities and schools have to work collaboratively in order to improve the quality of education. Hence, capacity building workshops engender change in human behaviour, attitudes, knowledge, skills, and capabilities focussed on cultivating professional etiquette required by teachers to perform adequately at given tasks.

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